

DEVELOPMENT EVIDENCES IN THE UNDERDEVELOPED COUNTRIES

Daniel Udouo Akpan¹ & Charles Edet Ekpe²

^{1, 2} Federal College of Education, Ididep, Ibiono Ibom, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria

EMAIL: danielchrist81@gmail.com¹, Charlesee2017@gmail.com²

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ABSTRACT

RESEARCH ARTICLE

This paper assesses development evidences in the underdeveloped countries.

The information on development in the underdeveloped countries were obtained from secondary source. The paper reveals that underdeveloped countries are characterized by vicious circle of poverty, adverse geographical condition with terrible weather condition. Also, the study shows that anti-development factors such as socio-cultural and ethnic division have often led to conflict and clashes in the underdeveloped countries coupled with high population growth rate and extreme income inequality, of which constraint development. In view of these findings, the study recommends that underdeveloped countries should prioritize the adoption of renewable energy, ensure sustainable economic growth and structural reforms. As well, the countries should promote girl child education, empowering women to make informed reproductive decisions and emphasize investment in both physical and human infrastructure.

KEYWORDS: *Development, evidences, underdeveloped, countries*

INTRODUCTION

Development journey is a complex, woven with threat and opportunity, especially in underdeveloped countries. Thus a threat according to World Bank Group, 2020 is a significant employment crisis as about 1.2 billion young people in underdeveloped countries are expected to reach working age within the next 10 to 15 years, while current economic projections indicate that around 400 million jobs are likely to be created during the same period. This mismatch, according to the report could leave hundreds of million without access to productive employment.

In addition, according to the President, World Bank Group, A Jay Banga, global attention is often captured by immediate crisis such as conflicts, technological disruption and market volatility, slower-moving structural forces like demographics, food and water pressure and globalization trends, which are likely to have deeper and longer-lasting consequences.

These are not only development issues but also an economic challenges with increasingly global security concern.

Gladly, development intervention icons such as Bill and Melinda Gates have distributed over 100 billion dollars in grants since 2000 to improve global health, reducing poverty and expanding educational opportunities.

Moreso, if there is one message from decades of global development research, from the rise of South Korea and Singapore to the struggles of Brazil, it is that no nation become develops by weak foundational literacy, limited vocational training and an overstretched university system wrestling with inadequate funding and brain drain. In other words, no country has ever industrialized without investing heavily in its people. The Korea's transformation, which is documented in every development textbooks, began not with factories but schools.

Interesting, if countries, especially underdeveloped countries, are serious about escaping stagnation, human capital development must become a national obsession, not a paragraph in policy document. This is where many Latin American countries are stalled. They industrialized early but did not develop strong domestic innovation systems, and eventually lost competitiveness in Asia.

In all, underdeveloped countries cannot achieve development with erratic internet, poor road network, unreliable electricity, and congested ports. Lessons from East Asia are striking. Korea built world-class highways and ports before it became developed and rolled out broadband ahead of most developed countries.

Conceptual Literature

Economic of development is a branch of economic, which studies economy and prospect of 82 percent of the world population about 5.8 billion called underdeveloped or developing countries or intermediate developing countries. Indeed, human beings are the centre of development, hence these countries are faced with multidimensional challenges such as multidimensional poverty, frightening unemployment, deprivation, extreme inequality etc.

Interestingly, development economics attempts to investigate the causes of poverty or low income of developing countries with a view to designing process to pull-out many out of poverty comprehensively. In other word, Economics of development emanated to solve multi-development economic problems with a focus on developing countries.

Interesting, development can be different thus to difference people. According to International Labour Organization, development is a process of maximizing output in order to minimize poverty. It is concerned with food adequacy(calories/nutritional value),decent housing, health, life expectancy, sanitation and other basic surviving needs such as water, electricity, road etc.

Accordingly, Amartya Sen, a noble laureate in Economic 1998 assessed development in terms of freedom, the ultimate goal of economic life as well as the most efficient way of realizing human welfare, overcoming deprivation such as hunger, famine, ignorance, unemployment, barriers to economic attainment by women/minority, no access to health facility and water.

Also development has been envisaged as an ideal for environmental management with emphases on the impact on environment such as pollution, especially industrial waste with

tendency to pollute the environment with a grave consequences on the health of society, causing a long-term poverty effect. In the view, the World Bank, environmental management without adequate control measures damages the society. This strengthens the resolves of the bank's modest influence on environment with a view to check poverty consequent caused by pollution.

In all, in contemporary analyses, development sits firstly on the pillars of sustenance; which means access to basic needs such as food, shelter and health on sustainable basis and elimination of absolute poverty considered as a necessary condition for improvements in the quality of life. Secondly, self-esteem, which emphasizes sense of worth, respect, technological advancement. Thirdly, freedom from servitude. This envisaged emancipation from alienation and situation such as slavery, misery, institutional and dogmatic beliefs.

Literature Review

According to World Bank (2023), highlighted significant hurdles including high debt burdens, climate-related risk, extreme poverty, huge range of disparities in health and education as the hinders of development in developing countries.

Human Development Report (2007), revealed that the high Gross National Product (GNP) growth of the fast growing has failed to reduce the socio-economic deprivation of the countries. High income for the industrialized countries has not been able to provide protection against the spread of social vices such as drug addiction and alcoholism, AIDs, homelessness, violence and breakdown of family relations.

The world faces a harsh reality of progress, ending extreme poverty everyday by 2030, crushing of debt burdens and rising fragility and conflict, devastating climate shock and extreme weather, which threaten or slow or reverse progress (World Bank Group, 2024).

Report by AFSIC 2026 shows Africa faces a complex array of development challenges that use deeply interconnected, ranging from structural economic issues to weak Institutions and environmental threat. Equally, according to UN trade and development, report in Africa, 2024 using a new framework, analyses the continuous vulnerabilities across six area; economic, governance, connectivity, social energy and climate. Also, the report revealed that within Africa, a few major economies; Kenya, Nigeria and South Africa dominate as suppliers and users of value-added goods, regional production network are vulnerable to disruption in key markets being the concern of development.

In all, countries particularly emerging economies are confronted with multi-dimensional challenges, spanning from economic, political, social to environmental factors. These underscored the need for comprehensive, sustained and long-term strategies to overcome.

Theoretical Literature on development examine the eviction of development from 1950. The key ones are:

1. Modernization Theory

This theory reveals that underdeveloped nations can achieve property by replicating the industrialization, technology and value shifts of the attention nations.

II. **Dependency Theory**

Posits that global inequalities are incalculated in exploitative relationships where the underdeveloped nations depends perpetually on the developed nations. This envisages a underdeveloped nations reliance on the development of the developed nations. This theory attributed to the work of Rawl Prebisch in the late 1950.

III. **Neoclassical / Neoliberal Theory:**

This theory focuses on free markets, deregulation and privatization to enhance development. This theory is attributed to the work of Alfred Marshall and Milton Fredman, who advocated for free-market capitalism, privatization and monetanism.

IV. **Human Development Approach**

This theory emphasizes that development should be measured by improvements in human life in the area such as health, education and freedom rather than just economic.

This theory was introduced by United Nations Development Programme in 1990 pioneered by Mahbleb ul Hag. The theory also, emphasizes access to knowledge, decent standard of living and a true wealth of nations.

Development is affected by with a number of challenges

1. **Lower level of living and productivity**

There is vast difference between the income of underdeveloped as synonymous to Africa and the developed nation.

According to World Bank, 2024 deepening poverty crises in Africa, particularly Nigeria, where the poverty rate may hit 62 percent by 2026, affecting 141 million people due to high inflation and high cost. The report emphasizes that 23 of the 28 poorest countries are in Africa; with 57 percent of the world's poor residing in Sub-Saharan Africa, driven by poor leadership, corruption and insecurity.

Accordingly, the report revealed that over one-third of people in countries eligible for support from the world IDA and more than half of the members are in Sub-Saharan Africa, experiencing multidimensional poverty, highlighting how persistent development challenges remain.

2. **Adverse Geographical Condition**

Development has been uneven, especially in the Sub-Saharan occasioned by terrible weather condition, which precipitated global warming. This is largely attributed to climate change, highlighting an respiratory threat to humanity. Weather-related disasters include devastating floods occasioned by intense rainfall in Africa, submerging homes and farm land and displacing family.

Equally, extreme weather severely damaged critical infrastructure such as road, power lines, water and sanitation facilities and cut off communities from essential services, besides, forcing thousand into secondary displacement. As well, the developed nations are not spared as heat wave; landslide devastated many residents.

3. **Greater Social Factionalization**

This is concerned with socio-cultural and ethnic division existence within a country. This often lead to strike, conflict and clashes. Obviously, most development resources and time are expended in search for unity, peace and coexistence. In essence, the present of high level factionalization explains the enormity of development challenge coupled with ethnic instability. The more the level of ethnic polarization, war, conflict, religious diversity, the likely the occurrence of internal strike, political instability and lack of development.

4. **High Population Growth Rate**

The demographers are pretty worried at the rate at which the population of the world is going, particularly in many of the developing countries. It is noted that having a large number is no longer an asset, it is now liability. Population decline is more pronounced in Eastern and Southern Europe while western and Northern European countries experience slower declines or even population growth due to migration.

The latest data published by the Australian Centre for Population showed a significant annual increase in the continent's population, driven by net overseas migration.

Conversely, Africa presently has the fastest growing population, projected to rise throughout the century, with the population rise than doubling by 2070.

5. **High level of Inequality**

Poverty and inequality are twin phenomenon that hinder growth and development. Indeed, the world is characterized by inequality. Globally 20 percent of people received 1.5 percent of the world income according to United Nation report, 2017. This disparity leads to extreme reduction in economy opportunity.

According to South African G20 presidency in 2025, the richest 1 percent increased their wealth 2,655 times more than the bottom 50 The number of billionaires now exceeds 3,000 globally and they hold wealth equivalent to 14.1 percent of the global GDP, up from 2.5 percent in 1990

Equally, the world inequality report 2026 reveals that global income inequality remains at very high levels, shaped by political and institutional choices rather than economic inevitability, warning that the concentration risk undermine democratic accountability and social cohesion.

In essence, the oxam research linked wealth imbalance to democratic challenges, occasioned by democratic erosion, political polarization etc,which translated into political inequality through concentrated media ownership and campaign finance power.

Findings

The study which assesses development evidences in underdeveloped countries, reveals the following findings:

Firstly, that the underdeveloped countries are riddled with lower level of living, attributed to slow economic growth, the lasting effect of COVID-19, crushing debt burdens and rising conflict.

Secondary, adverse geographical condition occasioned by bush burning, deforestation, indiscriminate land clearing, unregulated water extraction etc characterized to countries.

Thirdly, social factionalization such as ethnic conflict, racism, religious discrimination and discrimination against women fanned the ember of underdevelopment in the countries.

Furthermore, the rapid population poses serious threat on resource management, public service, job creation, health care and the overall quality of life.

In all, the study shows that the countries are evident with high income inequality, which hinders growth and development of which lead to extreme reduction in economy opportunities.

Recommendations

Firstly, global leaders must adopt solutions by reducing emissions through renewable energy and energy efficiency, investing in early warning systems, protecting and restoring ecosystem, promoting sustainable agriculture and transportation, enlarging individual, to save energy and use public transport particularly, Sub-Saharan Africa should vigorously address bush burning, deforestation, refuse dumping to reduce vulnerability to extreme weather events.

Secondly, countries must promote green, inclusive and sustainable economic growth to tackle the intertwined global challenges and jumpstart programme. This will create more opportunities for women and youth.

Thirdly, on social factionalization, there is need for structural reforms and inclusive governance to foster a more stable and productive society.

Fourthly, since population dynamics lies at the heart of economic, social and environmental s, countries should invest in education, health care, family planning and job creation. As well, promoting girl-child education and empowering women to make informed reproductive choices are important in controlling population growth. Also, harnessing technology, embracing vocational skills and investing in self- development are sustainable pathways to economic empowerment in a densely populated country.

In all, on inequality, institution should emphasize investment in both physical and human infrastructure, including reliable electricity, transport systems, healthcare and education.

Conclusion

If development is all about improving human life and provide wide range of opportunity, effort must be made to eliminate inequality, poverty and unemployment, as the development in the countries is characterized by jobless growth.

Obviously, without growth, there is no development. Therefore, the ongoing underdeveloped especially in developing countries exposes a failure of governance. Election cycle come and go, yet the realities faced by ordinary citizens remain unchanged.

In all, the research has shown that development, especially in the underdeveloped countries is fundamentally incomplete as the indices of lower level of living and productivity,

adverse geographical condition, greater social factionalization, high population growth and high level of inequality characterized the region

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